

Metadata for

Microstructure data – Bioconvective mixed layers in Lake Cadagno

This data repository includes 4 types of data files:

1. Microstructure data
e.g. dataVMP20170712.mat
2. Profile time data
e.g. dataVMP20170712_time_vmp1.txt
3. Mixed layer (ML) a priori depth location, obtained from eye inspection
e.g. dataVMP20170712_zl_tl_CORRECTED_20180809.txt
4. Radiation time series. Used to identify whether profiles were performed during day or night
e.g. dataVMP20170712_rad_analisys.mat

Data is organized by the starting date of the profiling campaign following: YYYYmmdd format

i.e. 20170828 corresponds to 28 August 2018

1. Microstructure data

Contains mat-files of microstructure profiles measured with a VMP-500 (Rockland Scientific)

Each file is a cell with $9 \times n$ elements, where n is the amount of VMP profiles. The content of each 9-element-column corresponds to:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
variable	Temp1	Temp2	P_fast	SB_T	SB_P	Cond1	Cond2	SB_C20	SB_C
Unit	°C	°C	dBar	°C	dBar	$\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$	$\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$	$\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$	$\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$
Sampling Frequency [Hz]	512	512	512	64	64	512	512	64	64

Temp1: fast thermistor 1 (FP07)

Temp2: fast thermistor 2 (FP07)

P_fast: Fast pressure sensor

SB_T: CTD Temperature (Sea Bird SBE-3)

SB_P: CTD Pressure (Sea Bird SBE-5T)

Cond1: Fast conductivity 1 (Sea Bird SBE-7 conductivity microsensors)

Cond2: Fast conductivity 2 (Sea Bird SBE-7 conductivity microsensors)

SB_C20: CTD 20 °C corrected conductivity

SB_C: CTD conductivity (Sea Bird SBE-4F)

The VMP data provided here is already cleared as described in the related publication (see repository description). Depths are calculated following:

$$\text{depth} = (P + P_{\text{offset}}) \times 1.0195$$

with P: Pressure

2. Profile time data

Contains approximate profile starting time (UTC + 2). Each file contents data following:

Column 1	Column 2	Column 3
hour	minutes	seconds

Each row corresponds to the profiles provided in the temperature microstructure data. The code vmp1, vmp2, vmp3 stands for the day 1, 2 or 3 of the profiling campaign.

3. Mixed layer (ML) a priori depth location

Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4	Column 5
VMP profile	Upper limit	Lower limit	Upper limit temperature	Lower limit temperature
#	m	m	°C	°C

The second YYYYmmdd formatted date after the tag: CORRECTED, stands for the day when the eye-inspection was performed.

4. Radiation time series

mat-file containing time series of radiation Each file of this type contains 2 arrays:

- ts: time in UTC
- radiation: radiation in $W m^{-2}$